

ARISE Policy Framework

Assistive Technology in Resilient and Inclusive Systems and Enabling Environments

Conceptualization

Policies should clearly and comprehensively define assistive technology.

Governance & Leadership

Policies should clearly lay out a coordinated governance structure and approach, with consideration for shared responsibility.

Service Delivery

Policies should reflect a commitment to a clearly articulated, evidence-based service delivery model addressing the entire AT access pathway and lifecycle.

Financing and Affordability

Policies should clearly specify how AT is financed and resourced.

AT Workforce

Policies should clearly address provider roles and competencies and workforce planning for AT provision.

Standards and Quality Assurance

Policies must establish clear quality and safety standards that protect users while remaining proportionate to actual risk and avoiding unnecessary barriers to market entry or product access.

Innovation, Research & Development

Policies should create environments fostering responsible innovation, while ensuring that innovation serves genuine user needs and reaches all populations.

Rights Protection and Advocacy

Policies should establish clear avenues for addressing violations of rights of access to, or use of assistive technology, support the capacity of AT users and their organizations to advocate for their rights, and implement measures preventing discrimination against AT users.

Awareness & Information

Policies should establish mechanisms for information platforms which provide accessible, current, and comprehensive information about available assistive products and services, eligibility criteria, provision pathways, and funding mechanisms.

Emergency Preparedness & Resilience

Policies should integrate emergency preparedness, ensuring that AT systems and AT users are protected during crises and that humanitarian responses adequately address AT needs.

Monitoring & Evaluation

Policies should establish comprehensive monitoring and evaluation systems addressing inputs, processes, outputs, outcomes, and impacts on broader system goals including equity, resilience, and sustainability.